

Forest Rehabilitation and Assessment of Important Elements of the Ecosystem Services of the Val d'Endor Watershed on the Island of Mahé, Seychelles – *Linking Research with Education*

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1. Introduction

1.1. Project background

The climate change projections in Seychelles show that rainfall, while increasing in overall terms, will become even more irregular (Kahn and Amelie, 2014). Much of the precipitation is falling in sharp bursts, creating heavy flooding in the wet season, while imposing an extended period of drought during the dry season. As island topography puts constraints on water storage capacity, the country's water supplies are heavily dependent on rainfall.

The project 'Ecosystem-Based Adaptation (EbA) to Global Change' in Seychelles, funded by the Adaptation Fund and implemented by UNDP and the Government of Seychelles, seeks to reduce the vulnerability of the Seychelles to climate change through the implementation of a series of pilot actions. This includes working in four water catchments on Mahé and one on Praslin to implement integrated adaptation measures including wetland enhancement and the management of catchment forests. In order to find ways of restoring ecosystem functionality and enhancing ecosystem services, such as water provisioning and flood attenuation from watersheds and coastal areas, the project requires a holistic assessment of the ecosystem services of water catchments in Seychelles and an evidence-based management approach for the rehabilitation of catchment forests.

1.2. Expected outcomes and underlying principles

The EbA project's aim is to reduce Seychelles' vulnerability to climate change, focusing on two key issues:

- ♦ Watershed rehabilitation
- ♦ Coastal rehabilitation, including coral reef rehabilitation

The present study deals with the first of these components, in an attempt to improve ecosystem services of the Val d'Endor watershed in regard to the following provisions:

Natural forests reduce the risk of flooding and secure water availability

Forests reduce erosion to a significant extent. River and coastal sedimentation affected by erosion may cause flooding and water quality deteriorations (i.e. increased NO₃-levels, high water turbidity, adverse effects to water distribution systems etc.) (Holmes and Likens, 2016; Corbett et al., 1978) as demonstrated further by the 'Hubbard Brook streamflow response to deforestation study' (Hornbeck et al., 1993):

- ♦ Most minerals were recycled within a natural forest ecosystem.
- ♦ The flow of minerals out of a natural watershed was offset by minerals flowing in.
- ♦ Deforestation increased surface water runoff¹ and hence erosion.
- ♦ The nitrate concentration in waters draining the deforested area became dangerously high.

In coastal areas, afforestation is a proven cost-effective method to dissipate wave energy and reduce flooding and inundation during storm surges. In a study by Mohiuddin et al. (2016), the effectiveness of afforestation as a buffer against the storm surge flooding is calculated. From this study it has been found that around 30% velocity, 32% to 35% thrust force and 11.41% inundated area are reduced due to coastal afforestation.

Natural forests filter pollutants and protect water quality

A review of treatment costs and watershed characteristics for 27 drinking water utilities found that for every 10% increase in forest cover of the source water area, chemical and treatment costs decrease by 20% (Ernst, 2004). A case study by Barnes et al. (2009) revealed that it is significantly more cost-effective to protect the watershed's natural land cover and forests to provide natural filtration, rather than installing a multi-billion dollar water treatment facility.

¹ Surface runoff is the flow of water that occurs when excess rainwater flows over the earth's surface. This can occur when the soil is saturated to full capacity, and rain arrives more quickly than soil can absorb it (Wikipedia, accessed November 2019).

Likewise, floodplains and natural landscapes minimize the impacts of floods, reduce the burden on public drainage infrastructure and increase groundwater recharge (Postel and Richter, 2003). And finally, healthy watersheds may increase property values: housing near healthy watersheds has higher property values than those in or around degraded ecosystems and impaired waters (EPA, 2005).

Does forest rehabilitation always have a positive effect on the hydrology of a watershed?

Tree growth can consume more water than other shorter vegetation (Lee and Zhang, 2018). According to the mass balance principle, if more water is used by trees, less water will flow into rivers and lakes or recharge the groundwater that people can directly use. The important question remains: how then can a positive effect of afforestation and forest rehabilitation on water supply be achieved? The following are important drivers for the hydrology of watersheds.

First: scale matters

Afforestation can accelerate the water cycle at a local and global level. For example, more than two square kilometres of forest expansion can increase the possibility of rainfall. Trees transport water to the air, and water vapour increases the possibility precipitation (Sheil, 2014).

Second: species matters

We must choose suitable tree species for forest rehabilitation to have a positive effect on the water discharge. Depending on the species, forests may have different amounts of water consumption and hence, different water discharge capacities (Schwärzel et al., 2018) The reasons for this are manifold:

♦ *Species have different water-use efficiencies (WUE)²*

Plants with a high WUE reduce their water demand. In general, the WUE is often low for young, alien, invasive forest stands. In Seychelles, the native Gondwana tree species may show a better water-use efficiency, because they are likely to be better adapted to a more arid Gondwana climate (Scotese, 1998). Tree water use also declines with age. Evidence shows, for example, that water supply may start to improve after 30 years in the case of pines and 15 years in the case of eucalypts (Scott and Prinsloo, 2008). Such facts give important guidance for a successful forest rehabilitation concept in Seychelles, in the sense that care should be taken to particularly focus on sustaining/supporting mature forest stands.

² Water-use efficiency: the ratio of dry biomass produced to the rate of transpiration (i.e. amount of water lost through leaf-transpiration) (Bramley et al., 2013).

- ♦ (2) *Species have different evapotranspiration rates (ETR)*³
It is assumed that invasive alien plants may have a greater impact on the hydrology of a watershed than native plant species. If there is indeed a significant impact of alien vs. native plants on available water resources, the main driver is undoubtedly their evapotranspiration rates (Travis, 2006). In some instances, invasive plants may increase evaporation rates and reduce stream flow (Chamier et al., 2012).
- ♦ (3) *Roots and the forest floor have an impact on the water provision.* The root structure and root depth are directly linked to water retention. Furthermore, root holes, arthropod- and wormholes increase macropore space and hence the water storage capacity of soil. The depth and surface of the forest floor greatly determine the infiltration of rainwater. Removing the forest floor can therefore reduce infiltration rates not only for the litter layer but also for underlying soil layers.

Third: climate change matters

Higher rates of evapotranspiration due to climate change increase the green water flux (i.e. water uptake by plants) and hence reduce the water discharge of a watershed. Furthermore, research by Laurance et al. (2014) supports the view that vines are increasing in abundance in old-growth tropical forests, possibly in response to rising CO₂ concentrations. This research gives reason to assume that climate change may deteriorate the ‘*Merremia peltata* drama’⁴ in Seychelles.

1.3. The Seychelles case

In order to assess the impact of alien vs. native plants on the potential water provision of a watershed, we cannot neglect the above mentioned issues, and scientists and decision-makers need to respectfully appreciate that this highly complex issue has not yet been sufficiently addressed or resolved in Seychelles, and hence, at present, nobody knows if and what kind of exotic tree species occurring in Seychelles’ watersheds may indeed have a bigger water demand than natives. This concern, however, does not mean that we are not fully convinced about the imperative and benefits of vegetation rehabilitation of watershed forests on Mahé and Praslin (Fleischmann, 2019). This important point of view is supported by the global assessment report by Creed and van Noordwijk (2018), stating that properly managed watersheds can indeed increase resilience of water supply

³ Evapotranspiration is the sum of evaporation and plant transpiration from the Earth's land and ocean surface to the atmosphere. Evaporation accounts for the movement of water to the air from sources such as the soil, canopy interception and waterbodies. Transpiration accounts for the movement of water within a plant and the subsequent loss of water as vapour through stomata in its leaves (Nan, 2011).

⁴ The vine *Merremia peltata* (Liane tortue) is one of the most aggressive alien invasive plants in the Seychelles, covering and killing thousands of potentially important forest trees and native palms (Master et al., 2013; Pierre and Fleischmann, 2016).

to enable adaptation to global change. In our view it seems essential to translate the basic aims of the EbA watershed project into a more holistic framework, focusing on the understanding of the key elements of the ecosystem service of watersheds, and on how this understanding can be used to address current and future challenges regarding water supply and water quality.

1.4. Research contributions of the University of Seychelles, the Federal Institute of Technology Zürich, the GoS/UNDP/GEF Coordination Unit, and the Save our Seas Foundation

This study is the product of 15 students from the University of Seychelles (UniSey), two master students from the Federal Institute of Technology (ETH) Zürich, Switzerland and five lecturers from ETH Zürich and UniSey. In 2016/17 the following elements of the ecosystem services and one of their adversaries were assessed in the Val d'Endor watershed: (1) *Vegetation quality*, (2) *Impact of anthropogenic activities* (potential polluters, building activities, logging, pressure on plant cover etc.), (3) *Water quality*, (4) *Water discharge*, (5) *Forest light climate* (as the main driver of plant invasions), (6) *Forest canopy structure* (using drones).

The 2019 revised edition of the full report 'Forest rehabilitation and assessment of important elements of the ecosystem services of the Val d'Endor watershed on the island of Mahé' (Fleischmann et al., 2019) is available at:

[https://www.pcusey.sc/index.php/component/remository/Ecosystem-Based-Adaptation-\(EBA\)-Project/Project-Technical-Reports/Technical-and-Other-Reports/EBA-Component-1/Baie-Lazare-River-Catchment/?Itemid=](https://www.pcusey.sc/index.php/component/remository/Ecosystem-Based-Adaptation-(EBA)-Project/Project-Technical-Reports/Technical-and-Other-Reports/EBA-Component-1/Baie-Lazare-River-Catchment/?Itemid=)

Since March 2017, some of the above-mentioned research aspects have been the subject of a Memorandum of Understanding between UniSey and the Seychelles Ministry of Environment, Energy and Global Change.

2. Methods and results

2.1. The vegetation quality (Massy, Schmutz, Fleischmann, Millett and Vel)

This study aimed at (a) providing a quotable and repeatable baseline for a watershed forest rehabilitation, and (b) developing a methodology for the pre- and post-rehabilitation monitoring of the Val d'Endor watershed (3.6 km²). Between January and July 2016 ten permanent vegetation-monitoring sites and more than two kilometers of forest transects were established at the Val d'Endor watershed on Mahé (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Permanent monitoring sites of the Val d'Endor watershed (10 transects and 10 sample plots in each site). (Source: Massy and Schmutz, 2016)

Such transects provided the necessary data: (I) to determine the prominence values (PV = relative species abundance + relative species frequency) of adult and juvenile woody plant species within the watershed (Table 1 and Fleischmann, 1997a); (II) to assess the forest quality (Fleischmann, 1997b) in terms of (a) the degree of endemism, (b) the rate of native forest regeneration, (c) native species diversity and (d) the abundance of native vs. alien species (Figure 2); (III) to estimate forest succession by comparing the relative abundance of adult vs. juvenile trees (Figure 3); (IV) to estimate the magnitude and the pattern of plant invasions in each monitoring site (Figure 4); (V) to develop vegetation rehabilitation guidelines. In addition, we established permanently marked 25m x 10m sampling plots in each of the 10 monitoring sites, giving an understanding of (1) the tree density; (2) the tree dominance⁵ and tree height; (3) the composition and structure of the ground cover and (4) the plot rejuvenation (i.e. the presence and state of emergent seedlings and saplings). Pictures of fifty 5m x 10m rectangle sub-plots were taken for future photo-monitoring.

⁵ The dominance of a tree species is the sum of the basal area (cross-sectional area) at breast height (1.3m above ground) of all trees in a stand and is usually expressed m²/ha (Larocque, 2019).

Table 1. Results of prominence values (PV) for adults and saplings of the 10 most prominent species found in the ten transects of the study area. Note: The red taxa stand for species endemic to the Seychelles.
(Source: Massy & Schmutz, 2016)

Species	PV (Adults)	PV (Saplings)
<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> (Cannelle)	26.5	19.57
<i>Tabebuia pallida</i> (Kalis-di-pap)	20.99	3.93
<i>Chrysobalanus icaco</i> (Coco plum)	20.02	24.67
<i>Phoenicophorium borsigianum</i> (Latannyen fey)	16.02	28.76
<i>Adenantha pavonina</i> (Agati)	11.81	14.86
<i>Sandoricum koetjape</i> (Santol)	11.04	11.32
<i>Memecylon eleagni</i> (Bwa kalou)	8.23	10.3
<i>Ochna ciliata</i> (Bois bouquet)	7.26	15.88
<i>Falcataria moluccana</i> (Albizzia)	6.71	1.31
<i>Paragenipa lancifolia</i> (Kafe maron gran fey)	6.61	5.92

Figure 2. The Val d'Endor forest quality in terms of Protection Values (PtV) after Fleischmann (1997). Note: PtV5 = highest and PtV1 = lowest vegetation quality in terms of (a) native species' regeneration, (b) the presence of endemics, (c) the diversity of natives and (d) the occurrence of invasive alien vs. native tree species. (Source: Massy and Schmutz, 2016)

Figure 3. Possible future changes in species composition (forest succession). Note: if the abundance of saplings is above the cut-off line (dashed line) it is likely that the abundance of these species will increase during their adult stage. In this example adult Cinnamon trees have a rel. abundance of 34, while in the same monitoring site Cinnamon saplings show a rel. abundance of only 6. It is therefore assumed that the abundance of Cinnamon will decrease in future.
 (Source: Massy & Schmutz, 2016)

Figure 4. Distribution map of the relative abundance of *Cinnamomum verum* (Cannelle).

Abundance classes: rel. abundance in transect 1-10 = low degree of invasion,
11-30 = medium invasion, >30 high invasion.

(Source: Massy and Schmutz, 2016. Pictures, upper picture, unknown author, accessed 22 September 2016 from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Cinnamomum_verum1.jpg.

Lower picture, Mélanie Schmutz 2016)

In regard to the forest quality, we have identified three sites with medium and high-quality vegetation (Figure 2), while all the other seven sites present a rather low vegetation quality (i.e. low abundance of endemic tree species, high abundance of exotics, medium to low regeneration of native trees and low diversity of natives). These three sites require a high priority for rehabilitation primarily by sustaining natural regeneration and by exercising the concept of a novel ecosystem management ⁶.

In regard to future changes in species distribution and forest succession our results have been instrumental for the design of forest rehabilitation recommendations. Note: all details are given in the online report.

⁶ Novel ecosystem management aims at maximizing genetic, species, and functional diversity wherever possible in order to preserve the viability of plant communities. This might imply not just removing species that are not desired in the first place, but managing the system in a way that their present ecological function is not reduced in view of (a) assisting natural regeneration of native tree species and (b) helping to avoid soil erosion (Kueffer et al., 2013).

2.2. The human impact (Massy, Schmutz and Krütli)

The human impact on the ecosystem services and, more specifically, the hydrological service of the Val d'Endor watershed were analysed by means of a characterization of current human activities (e.g. water management, agriculture etc.) and by other external factors (e.g. forest structure and weather) having a bearing on the watershed. Based on a literature review, informal talks and semi-structured interviews, we proposed impact variables ⁷ by which the structure and dynamics of the system of the Val d'Endor watershed could be characterised.

These impact variables were used for the construction of the following scenarios: (1) *intensive housing*, (2) *increased farming*, (3) *better protected water catchment*, and (4) *better regulated intensification of farming and housing*. These scenarios describe how the watershed might evolve for the next 30 years. The scenarios were evaluated in terms of *desirability* and *probability* by seven stakeholder groups having an influence on the watershed.

'*Intensive housing*' (Figure 5), is the most likely development scenario at Val d'Endor. Since the rate of precipitation infiltration is reduced by constructing impervious surfaces (Price, 2011), new settlements along with the building of roads and parking lots etc. will decrease water infiltration and retention and increase surface runoff after (heavy) rainfall events (Diersing, 2009). An increase of settlements may amplify the risks of flooding and water scarcity during extreme events. The '*increased farming*' scenario bears the second highest probability (Figure 5). Since the quality of water is strongly influenced by agricultural and domestic activities (e.g. use of pesticides and fertilizers, infiltration of faeces etc.) it is likely that soil and water pollution may increase in future and thus have an impact on human health.

⁷ Impact variables can be seen as physical, biological, chemical or social stressors, which potentially trigger changes in the system. Some of the variables used in this report are housing, water abstraction, water consumption, sanitation system and waste dumping (Massy and Schmutz, 2016).

Figure 5. Overall “desirability” versus “probability” for each scenario. Note: 0 = not at all desirable/probable; 10 = very desirable/probable.

(Source: Massy and Schmutz, 2016)

Concerning desirability, results show a preference for the two development scenarios ‘regulated intensification of housing and farming’ and ‘better protected water catchment area’ (all stakeholders agreed!). It is important to note that they entail both, stricter regulations regarding the protection of rivers, as well as the protection of forests and land. Though, we value the ‘desirability’ aspect of the above-mentioned scenarios as a positive outcome, it is somewhat discouraging to learn that the respondents rank the probability factor for the ‘better protected water catchment’ scenario as the lowest. The results show that all stakeholder groups rate the importance of the watershed as very high and support its rigorous protection. A sustainable development and proper planning are therefore critical for the future of the Val d’Endor.

2.3. The water quality (Fleischmann, Mendez, UniSey students and Vel)

The global challenge

Worldwide one in ten people lack access to safe water – this is twice the population of the United States – and one in three people lack access to a toilet; i.e. more people have a mobile phone than a toilet (Banzai, 2015). Almost two billion people were affected by natural disasters in the last decade, 86% of them by floods and droughts (World Disaster Report, 2018). In Seychelles flooding, agricultural practices, inadequate sanitation, and refuse dumps etc. increase the ever-present health threat from contamination of drinking-water systems. This is why the public and local decision makers need to appreciate the importance of clean water and the enormous ecosystem service of Seychelles’ watersheds.

Water quality monitoring

From January 2016 onwards, 6 permanent water-sampling points at Val d'Endor (Figure 6) have been regularly visited by students of the UniSey Env. Sc. Department to collect water samples to be analysed. The related data provide a baseline information to identify trends or changes in water quality caused by point- or nonpoint-source pollution and nutrient enrichment. Our data are cross-referenced with the water quality standards of the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), which are more or less consistent with the water quality indices of most European countries (Grohmann et al., 2003).

The quality parameters

The water quality analysis was performed as a joint venture between UniSey and the Seychelles Bureau of Standards (SBS). The following water quality indicators were analysed in-house at the UniSey Anse Royale campus by means of VERNIER sensors⁸: (1) ammonium, (2) biological oxygen demand (BOD), (3) dissolved oxygen (DO), (4) nitrate (NO₃), (5) pH, (6) total dissolved solutes (TDS) (i.e. conductivity), and (7) water turbidity; whereas quality parameters such as (a) *E. coli*, (b) nickel, (c) lead, (d) phosphate, (e) sodium, and (f) total coliform have been jointly analysed by SBS.

The relative contamination/quality index (CI/QI)

The actual water quality data given in the Appendix, Part III in the online report are expressed in absolute values (mg/l). In order to make the data easier to read and to be able to better compare the data among the six sampling sites, a combined *Contamination Index (CI)/Quality Index (QI)* was introduced. The CI provides a means of comparing the %-magnitude of the water contamination with pollutants found at each site. The highest contamination is assigned as CI=100; the opposite stands for the quality index, for which QI=100 means highest water quality.

Outcomes

The degree of contamination by each pollutant can be seen in Table 2.

Site 4 (chicken farm) scores 5 out of the 12 highest CI values, and site 5 (Esparon) scores 6 out of the 12 second highest CI values. Both sites indicating the lowest water quality found in the Val d'Endor catchment. Whereas 10 out of 12 water quality indices score highest at site 3 (Vidot), indicating that site 3 enjoys the highest water quality at Val d'Endor.

⁸ VERNIER develops new data-collection technology, integrating sensors (e.g. dissolved oxygen sensor, detecting the amount of dissolved oxygen in a water sample), loggers and statistical devices for the analysis of soil, air and water quality

Table 2. Summary of all contamination index (CI) values at sampling sites 1 to 6.
(Source: Fleischmann, 2019)

Pollutant	Sampling sites					
	Site 1 Bougainville	Site 2 Lepathy	Site 3 Vidot	Site 4 Chicken farm	Site 5 Esparon	Site 6 Main road
Ammonium	27	32	24	100	60	25
BOD	7	100	8	49		4
Chloride	63	75	53	76	81	100
Total coliform	13	14	1	28	100	57
E. coli	4	10	1	93	100	56
Lead	100	34	0	0	27	0
Nickel	19	39	23	73	91	100
Nitrate	31	63	4	100	50	78
Phosphate	91	53	47	100	57	43
Sodium	100	99	75	79	81	100
TDS	73	85	49	100	89	87
Turbidity	100	92	60	94	88	79
Rel. CI_{mean}	52.3	58.0	28.8	74.3	74.9	60.8

A ranking of the water quality in terms of the average contamination index (CI) values is as follows (Table 3):

- ◆ *Best water quality*, site 3 (Vidot), relative CI = 28.8.
- ◆ *Lowest water quality*, site 5 (Esparon), relative CI = 74.9.

Table 3. The two highest and the lowest contamination index (CI) values for each sampling site at Val d'Endor.
(Source: Fleischmann, 2019)

Pollutant	Highest CI value in catchment	Second highest CI value in catchment	Lowest CI value in catchment
Ammonium	Site 4	Site 5	Site 3
Biological oxygen demand	Site 2	Site 4	Site 6
Chloride	Site 6	Site 5	Site 3
Total coliform	Site 5	Site 6	Site 3
E. coli	Site 4	Site 5	Site 3
Lead	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3
Nickel	Site 6	Site 5	Site 1
Nitrate	Site 4	Site 6	Site 3
Phosphate	Site 4	Site 1	Site 3
Sodium	Site 1	Site 2	Site 3
Total dissolved solids	Site 4	Site 5	Site 3
Turbidity	Site 1	Site 5	Site 3

We are concerned that the lowest water quality goes to the catchment with the highest average water discharge (in average 615 m³/d; see 2.4.) in the Val d'Endor watershed.

Based on the water quality parameters used in this project, the quality of river water at Val d'Endor can be described as good. All parameters examined meet the EPA & European drinking water standards except (1) the ammonium content at site 4 (chicken farm), (2) total coliform, and (3) E. coli found at all sites, except site 3 (Vidot). The bacteriological tests indicate the need for chlorination of drinking water from the Val d'Endor watershed. It is important to note that our analysis did not include strongly recommended tests for pesticides used at Val d'Endor; in particular the use of the glyphosate 'Roundup' (Daily Mail, 2015) and the still widely used contact herbicide 'Paraquat'.

Notes of concern

Our findings indicate that the river water at sites 4 (chicken farm) and 5 (Esparon) was clearly impacted by human activities, resulting in the poorest overall water quality in the Val d'Endor watershed. These disturbing results indicate that we may have to talk about a point-source pollution at both sampling sites. We strongly recommend communicating this inconsistency to the Ministry of Environment.

Site 1 (Bougainville) showed the highest overall water turbidity (i.e. 17.9 NTU with a CI value of 100). This site often shows red-earth infiltration as a consequence of uncontrolled and probably illegal landscaping (i.e. removal of top-soil for a hydroponics project just above the tributary wetland to sampling site 1). We are concerned about this finding as well, since the Bougainville site is the third most important catchment area at Val d'Endor in terms of water discharge (i.e. in average 289 m³/d). We advise a follow-up investigation of this issue by the Ministry of Environment.

There is, however, no doubt that the overall water quality at site 3 (Vidot) is the best in the whole Val d'Endor watershed.

2.4. The water discharge – river and groundwater provision (Persaud, Fleischmann, Mendez, UniSey students and Vel)

River and groundwater ecosystems provide services that are of immense societal and economic value (Griebler and Avramov, 2015). Now, that we have gained an insight into the water quality at Val d'Endor, it is equally important to find an estimation of the freshwater discharge as an additional ecosystem service of this important watershed.

Downstream domestic and commercial consumers and plant and animal species depend on this water, which is an increasingly scarce resource in Seychelles. Although the study carried out by Emerton (1997) found no existing data on which to assess the monetary value of ecosystem services provided by watersheds in Seychelles, it can be assumed that the value is high (Hepelwa, 2014; Berghöfer, 2016). Water-use issues are one of the primary and most persistent threats to biodiversity and therefore merit the central focus of the Seychelles' National Biodiversity Strategy and Action Plan (SNBSAP) implementation unit in their efforts to mainstream biodiversity.

Between April 2016 and April 2017, the water discharge at Val d'Endor has been monitored in seven separate monitoring sessions by students of the UniSey Env. Sc. Department under the supervision of Dr. Indra Persaud.

These periodic water flow assessments have been performed at the permanent sampling sites shown in (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Permanent water sampling points at Val d'Endor.
(Source: Persaud and Mendez, 2016)

To calculate water-flow rates and stream discharge (i.e. the volume of water moving downstream, usually expressed in m^3/s) two techniques are used: A V-notch weir and a portable flowmeter. At Val d'Endor, V-notch weirs (Figure 7) have been installed at some sites, but where there are no weirs, a flowmeter was used instead.

Figure 7. V-Notch weir at sampling site 6.
(Photo credit: Lara Kalisch, UniSey)

Measuring water flow with a V-notch weir

A weir is an overflow dam used to alter the flow characteristics of a river or stream. In most cases weirs take the form of a barrier across the river that causes water to pool behind the structure but allows water to flow over the top. Weirs allow hydrologists a simple method of measuring the volumetric flow rate in small to medium-sized streams (Munson et al., 2002). Since the geometry of the top of the weir is known, and all water flows over the weir, the depth of water behind the weir can be converted to a rate of flow. The V-notch is most commonly a 90° opening with the sides of the notch inclined 45° with the vertical. Given that Seychelles experiences heavy seasonal rains, a wide angle of 120° is used for the V-notch, to reduce the risk of the stream breaching the weir.

The following formula allows an estimation of the water flow with a 120° V-notch:

$$Q \text{ (m}^3\text{/s)} = 2.47 * H^{2.48}$$

Where:

H = head above lowest point of V-notch (meters)

Q = discharge (m³/s)

Measuring water discharge with a flow meter

The calculation involves measuring the cross-sectional area of a river by measuring the height of the water surface at equidistant, rectangular subsections (Figure 8) multiplied by the width of the corresponding subsection.

Figure 8. The calculation of the cross-sectional area of a river.
 (Source: Fondriest environmental learning centre)

For a river with a width less than 5m (which was the case at all sites) the depth can be measured at quarterly intervals. The sum of all subsection areas is then the cross-sectional area of the river. To calculate the water discharge (Q), the cross-sectional area (A) of water in a channel is multiplied by the average velocity (V) of water at each subsection; i.e. $Q = V \cdot A$. The average velocity from all subsections is measured by means of a flow meter in m/s.

Over a period of one year the average daily discharge in the Val d'Endor watershed was 1584 m³/d, with a maximum of 3224 m³/d on April 11th 2016 and a minimum of 57 m³/d on October 10th 2016. The underlying results are given in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Water discharge at the Val d'Endor watershed 2016/17.
(Source: Persaud Indra in Fleischmann, 2019)

We found the two highest flow rates at site 5 with 1587 m³/d and at site 2 with 1252 m³/d. The three highest average discharges per day over a period of one year go to site 5 (616 m³/d), site 2 (298 m³/d) and site 1 (289 m³/d), whereas the lowest average discharge was seen at site 6 (35 m³/d). Site 5 was not only the leading water provider, but also proved (together with site 1) to be the steadiest in terms of water discharge (i.e. the discharge never dropped to zero m³/d at site 5 and only once at site 1).

2.5. The forest light climate (Bandara, Fleischmann, Murugaiyan, Massy, Schmutz and UniSey students)

In the course of the Val d'Endor forest study it became obvious, that alien invasive plants posed the single most important impact on the watershed vegetation. Since the light climate must be a primary subject of an investigation in regard to the invasibility⁹ of a forest by alien invasive plant species, we attempted to quantify and characterize the light environment in the Val d'Endor watershed area. For this purpose, a technique, which allows a quantitative evaluation of light conditions throughout the year was required.

The characterization of the forest light climate

Hemispherical canopy photography is a technique for studying plant canopies using photographs taken through a hemispherical (fisheye) lens from beneath a canopy looking

⁹ The invasibility of a habitat is dependent on the structure of the resident ecological network and is defined as the level of vulnerability of a habitat to invasions from outside species (Hui et al., 2016).

upward. Such hemispherical photographs provide an extreme wide-angle with a 180° field of view. The photographs can be analysed to estimate light levels beneath the canopy. Thus, canopy photographs can be used to assess a local light environment beneath plant canopies. An image-specific threshold selection (optimum image brightness value) allows the distinction between the vegetation and sky patches (Figure 10). A computer program translates the canopy openness into a diffuse site factor (DifSF), which is the fraction of incident diffuse radiation transmitted by holes in the canopy reaching the forest floor (Rich et al.,1993).

Figure 10. A comparison of a hemispherical photograph (left) and a digitalized image of the same photograph (right). Arrows show how reflections of leaves (which can be misinterpreted as canopy openings) are eliminated by applying a suitable grey level threshold.
(Source: Fleischmann, 1997b)

Diffuse Site Factor (DifSF) vs. Direct Site Factor (DSF)

In this study the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), as the essential factor for growth and seedling and sapling establishment, was estimated in the form of DifSF rather than sunfleck activity. The reasoning for this approach is provided in a publication by Fleischmann (1997c), giving details such as why a predicted DifSF gives a sufficiently accurate estimation of PAR in a particular site.

The way the light climate has been assessed

In order to determine the effect of canopy openness (DifSF) to plant invasions, 90 hemispherical canopy photographs were taken along transects within the 10 permanent monitoring sites at Val d'Endor. Provided that there are no significant seasonal changes in the canopy, which is the case in the tropics, a single photograph can be used to estimate the potential radiation received during the year. The technique appears particularly useful for providing relative comparisons between forest sites.

The hemispherical photographs were taken using a Nikkor lens (AF DX Fisheye-Nikkor 10.5mm f/2.8G ED) attached to a Nikon D7200 camera. In order to achieve an optimal image quality each photograph was taken (1) in the automatic mode and (2) at a 1/100 shutter speed using an appropriate aperture opening and the focusing setting into infinity. The camera was mounted due North on a levelled tripod 1.3 m above ground. The photographs were taken in full-colour tones, always between 8-10 a.m. and 2-6 p.m.,

as recommended by Whitmore (1993). Afterwards, we turned all the pictures taken into images in grey tones. This is a necessary transformation in order to run the software 'Mat-Lab', which we applied to analyse the set of hemispherical photographs and the area of each canopy gap.

Determination of the threshold value for 'black' pixels

Since the image-analysis system does not distinguish canopy openings from reflective foliage the interpretation of a digitized image can be biased. Such a potential problem (i.e. user bias) is demonstrated in Figure 10 where the reflective foliage of *Vanilla planifolia* (see arrows) can be misinterpreted as canopy openings. To overcome this problem a grey level threshold had to be determined for each analysis by comparing the canopy photograph with its digitized image. Only points with a grey level below a preselected threshold were then sampled and scored for openness by the image analysis system. To manipulate the data and define the threshold the 2016 version of *R-Language* was used.

Determination of the weighting factors

Pixels of the digitalized image (Figure 10) that are 'black' must be weighted by a factor that scales each for its contribution to the total illumination from the sky. Assuming that the sky is brighter overhead, DifSF was weighted following the procedure described by Pearcy (1983). It is understood that canopy holes near the zenith did proportionally contribute more than those near the horizon. The computer program (2016 version of 'Mat-Lab') calculated specific weighting factors by taking the location of a pixel on the equiangular projection into account (i.e. pixels in the centre of the projection are weighted higher than pixels at the periphery).

The weighted canopy openness (i.e. the DifSF) is then the total number of open points multiplied by their weighting factors, divided by the total number possible in an unobstructed sky, as well multiplied by their weighting factors (Chazdon and Field, 1987).

As already mentioned, we used diffuse site factors (DifSF) to characterize and quantify the light climate in the Val d'Endor watershed, and the results are given in Figure 11.

Figure 11. Mean diffuse site factors (DifSF) taken from 90 hemispherical canopy photographs, representing the light climate of the 10 permanent monitoring sites in the Val d'Endor watershed forest. Note that within a single monitoring site 18 assessments (9 manual- plus 9 automatic aperture settings) were used. In this diagram each assessment is represented by a small circle. The average diffuse site factor within the 10 monitoring sites is $DfSF = 10.9$.

(Source: Fleischmann et al., 2019)

With an estimated mean DifSF of 18.68 Dan Marizan North showed the highest lighting level within the 10 permanent monitoring sites. Here the diffuse site factors showed the highest variance ($Stdv. = 21.23$) within all sites, representing a rather open forest with patches of darker areas where palms (especially *Phoenixophorium b.* and *Nephrosperma v.*) are established. The opposite is true for Dan Tombalo low, for both estimated mean DifSF (2.75) and light variance ($Stdv. = 1.84$). The light climate at Dan Tombalo low can be compared with one of the darkest forest parts in the Vallée de Mai World Heritage Site. It has been seen that with the exception of Dan Marizan North lighting levels within the 10 monitoring sites do not seem to vary a lot, confirming similar forest structures within the Val d'Endor catchment forest. This is an important prerequisite when selecting representative forest areas for the establishment of permanent monitoring sites. Taking the light climate of the Vallée de Mai¹⁰ as a standard for a mature, native forest, it can be seen that the estimated diffuse site factors in the Val d'Endor catchment forest are slightly higher. It is expected that this might change towards a darker light climate after forest rehabilitation, especially in those areas where the native palms are utilized as the favoured species for forest rejuvenation. Perceiving that light is the main

¹⁰ The light climate in the Vallée de Mai World Heritage Site: in this unique old-growth forest the diffuse light was estimated by means of 95 hemispherical canopy photographs, representing the light climate in six permanent monitoring sites: Site 1, DifSF 6.7; site 2, DifSF 5.2; site 3, DifSF 3.8; site 4, DifSF 4.5; site 5, DifSF 2.1; site 6, DifSF = 4.0. Average DifSF of all monitoring sites = 4.4 (Fleischmann et al., 2005).

driver for plant invasions (Terra et al., 2012; Bellingham et al., 1996), this research component highlights the usefulness of hemispherical canopy photography and the importance of a continued monitoring of the light climate in the Val d'Endor watershed.

Light as an important driver for plant invasions

Fleischmann (1999) found significant correlations between the competitive ability (demographic score¹¹) of the highly invasive cinnamon (*Cinnamomum verum*) versus the endemic latanyen fey palm (*Phoenicophorium borsigianum*) at three different light levels (DifSF) in a palm forest at La Résèrve (Montagne Posée), Mahé.

For cinnamon there were significant positive correlations with growth (i.e. increments/y in leaf area and height) and survival. This means that a species like *Cinnamomum v.* tends to have a higher competitive ability with increasing levels of the photosynthetically active radiation (PAR). For *Phoenicophorium b.* the seedling performance was significantly reduced in areas of above average light. Unlike *Cinnamomum v.*, the endemic *Phoenicophorium b.* tends to have a higher competitive ability in shadier forest sites. This important paradigm was implemented in the forest rehabilitation concept at Val d'Endor, using *Phoenicophorium b.* and other endemic palms like *Nephrosperma v.*, *Deckenia n.* and *Verschaffeltia s.* as the favoured flagship species for forest rehabilitation.

Forest light climate and forest rehabilitation

Phoenicophorium b. can be considered a high canopy specialist. Its shade tolerance and capacity to grow even at very low light levels make this palm particularly successful in competing with *Cinnamomum v.* and probably other invaders in shaded forest areas. As mentioned in 2.1. when removing invasive alien trees, we follow the concept of a 'novel ecosystem management', based on the principle that removing plant invaders needs to be done in a way that their present ecological function is not compromised. We therefore always aim at a most restrictive and selective cutting of adult trees. Felling is best performed where rejuvenation of natives is secured, e.g. in areas with natural rejuvenation of native palms, or where seedlings are being planted. The workforce exercising forest rehabilitation should therefore be advised to create as few forest gaps as possible – managing already established seedlings and saplings in a forest stand is more important than cutting trees!

¹¹ In this study, demographic score (i.e. competitive ability) was defined by (1) growth increment/y of plant height, (2) growth increment/y of leaf area, (3) plant mortality/y (and survival, resp.), (4) colonization/y (i.e. new recruits/y in 1m x 1m plots).

2.6. The forest canopy structure (Scholl, Fleischmann and UniSey students)

In many areas of nature conservation, drones can be a game changer. They enable researchers and conservationists to create quickly and cheaply their own high-resolution maps and 3D models that can then be used to identify plant species, to analyse canopy structures and to answer questions relating to the environment (Scholl et al., 2017).

One of the EbA project's challenges is the monitoring of post-rehabilitation changes and to sustain the forest rehabilitation efforts in future. The best possible way to monitor forest structure and species composition is an on-going drone-assisted canopy survey of the watershed forest. Moreover, a drone survey not only addresses the post-rehabilitation forest succession, and hence the success of forest rehabilitation efforts, but also provides practical aspects like research into the health of a forest, enabling a rapid response to environmental impact events (e.g. assessment of storm damage) and the monitoring of legal and illegal activities such as logging, building, farming activities, landscaping and waste dumping etc. As we have seen in 2.2. these factors are indeed most relevant for a successful watershed management.

A DJi Phantom-4 drone equipped with an integrated DJi camera (12.3 megapixel 1/2.3" CMOS sensor) was deployed at each of the ten intensive monitoring sites at Val d'Endor and the maps were made by flying the drone over the catchment forest following the exact GPS locations given in each transect (Figure 12).

Figure 12. Forest transects at the Dan Marizon permanent monitoring site.
(Source: Fleischmann and Scholl, 2016)

The drone-images (Figure 13) have enabled us to differentiate between similarly structured vegetation such as lowland and submontane forest, glacis type vegetation, bush, fern mats etc. The actual survey was single-handedly carried out by Michael Scholl, the CEO of the Save our Seas (SOS) Foundation. We would like to thank Michael Scholl for assisting the project with this essential research aspect and the SOS Foundation for the generosity in providing the drone and logistical support.

*Figure 13. Drone images along forest transect at the Dan Marizan North permanent monitoring site (the transect line is represented by the red line)
(Photo credit: Michael Scholl)*

The drone-assisted canopy survey at Val d'Endor is based on the GPS-data given in the Appendix, Part VI of the online report, and further data of the drone survey are available on request from Terence Vel, University of Seychelles (terence.vel@unisey.ac.sc).

3. Discussion and conclusion

Why protect healthy watersheds

Ecosystem services from healthy watersheds are the benefits Seychellois receive from nature. However, as we have seen in 2.2. and 2.3. these essential services and the natural

resources they depend on are placed at risk by processes driving landscape change, such as land-use policies and climate change. Ecosystem services are abundant in the Val d'Endor watershed, from clean drinking water and harvested forest products to erosion and flood control, carbon storage opportunities, increased resilience in the face of climate change threats, and reduced risk for invasive species colonization. Talking about the economic benefits of protecting Seychelles' watersheds, we need to appreciate that they not only reduce damage to property and infrastructure due to flooding, but also lower capital costs for drinking water treatment and infrastructure costs.

Linking research with education

The young University of Seychelles needs 'real life' research opportunities for students. Along with the participation in this EbA watershed project and in the framework of the required UniSey course component 'Research Methods and Skills in Environmental Science' (SENV1102) students were exposed to:

- ♦ The VERNIER analysis concept for water and soil testing.
- ♦ Principles of a vegetation survey.
- ♦ BioStatistics with StatPlus.
- ♦ Computerized assessment of forest light climates.
- ♦ Basic scientific writing, literature review, and critical analysis.
- ♦ Practical experience with regards to data collection, data analysis and interpretation in relation to environmental investigations

Research can no longer be seen as simply discovering or creating knowledge, and teaching is more than simply the transmission of what is already known. It has been seen that there are significant positive relationships between research and teaching (Colbeck, 2004). Breen (2002) found that students participating in real-life research showed an enhanced discipline-specific motivation, which had a substantial influence on student performance. This is because active learning is more likely to encourage students to adopt a deep approach to learning (Biggs, 2003; Prosser and Trigwell, 1999). Further evidence comes from the work of Baxter Magolda (1999) and Blackmore and Cousin (2003), who show that students involved in research-based inquiries develop more sophisticated levels of intellectual development.

Linking the project with local communities

The Val d'Endor watershed project presents the opportunity to integrate local communities, NGOs, and experts. For instance, community activities (such as weeding, tree nursery) are already on the way at Val d'Endor; and there are plans for long-term monitoring (of water quality, water flow, vegetation, human impacts) to be carried out by UniSey students in collaboration with the Federal Institute of Technology Zürich and the Seychelles Bureau of Standards. It is all about ownership, and it is our belief that a

project will fail, in the long run, if it is not carried out by the community concerned (Fleischmann, 2019).

Bringing new life to old partnerships

In the 1990s Karl Fleischmann established a research partnership initially focusing on vegetation monitoring as a basis for identifying conservation priority areas and for planning invasive species management efforts. This collaboration was further developed and diversified by Christoph Kueffer and Eva Schumacher, who still play an active role in the Seychelles Plant Conservation Action Group. Under the lead of Pius Krütli, the Transdisciplinary Lab (TdLab) of ETH Zürich initiated, in 2015, a long-term collaboration with UniSey and the Seychelles Ministry of Environment, Energy and Climate Change (MEECC). And finally, this long-standing partnership between UniSey, ETH and the MEECC reached a new zenith through the present EbA Val d'Endor watershed project.

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